

Opportunities for Data Exchange

THE ODE PROJECT / PUBLISHERS

Opportunities for Data Sharing

There is a growing consensus in science, and society generally, that primary research data resulting from publicly funded research should be shared widely so that the maximum benefits can be gained from the investment. There are common barriers and some reluctance, but also powerful drivers and benefits related to putting this general principle into practice.

Why should you as a publisher care about data sharing?

As a publisher you are probably aware of the increased demand on, and from, authors to make the data underpinning their research articles available. In many fields, journals have adapted to the growing practice of linking to and from datasets deposited in data

archives and subject specific repositories such as GenBank, Pangaea and the Worldwide Protein Data Bank. Other journals, often in areas with less well organised central data repositories, have experienced an explosive increase in the amount of supplementary material added to journal articles, mainly data sets.

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Do you know about others' views?

The EU FP7-funded ODE project has collected views from numerous individuals – representative of all stakeholder groups involved – on the opportunities for data exchange. These views were analysed and consolidated in order to inform each group about each others' views and possible future activities.

What ODE has learned:

Researchers and research funders increasingly view research data as a primary research output in its own right. Continued accessibility, interpretability and re-use of such data are therefore high on the agenda. Providing access to data in publications is therefore set to become more and more common.

Publishers have an important role to play in helping data centres to create a robust and long term infrastructure to ensure the findability and re-usability of research data as part of scholarly communication. Clear conventions about data citation will help authors gain credit for their data and will help increase the impact of available research data. Libraries, data centres and funders agree that this framework for recognition

should be developed in co-operation with publishers.

What you and your organization can do:

Publishers have many opportunities in the new era of open data to cater for these demands.

Editorial policies that require authors to make the data underlying their articles available have proven to be an immensely useful incentive for better availability of data. In addition, data journals and the acceptance of data articles in traditional journals can be encouraged further.

Trustworthy data archives are often a better place for research data than supplementary materials, as they can better ensure their long term preservation and permanent access. Publishers can work closely with data centres to ensure permanent bi-directional linking between data and publications.

Establishing good and consistent data citation practices together with data centres and libraries will help researchers to gain credit for their shared data and encourage good data management practice.

Data is the new gold.

"We have a huge goldmine... Let's start mining it."

Neelie Kroes, Vice-President of the European Commission responsible for the Digital Agenda
<http://europa.eu/rapid/pressReleasesAction.do?reference=SPEECH/11/872&type=HTML>

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